

Ere Festival Among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria

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The Ere festival is the most common annual ritual among the Ikale people. It has been an annual ritual event from the inception of the Kingdom, since the migration of their forebears from the Benin Kingdom. The Ikale, for decades were known to possess nine kingdoms, usually referred to as Ikale mehan (that is, the nine kingdoms of the Ikale). Ere is usually a celebrative ritual of the harvest where the kingdom declares its surplus. It is usually celebrated at Enu Owa (that is, the front of the palace) and is characterised by drinking, eating, singing, drumming, and dancing. The royal families often display their masquerades who would dance around the communities in the company of members of the families, before returning to the King's place for the grand finale. Ere was first observed in the old Akotogbo town around a geographical location known as Arogbo-Ule in 1522. It is important to note that this community is the oldest of all the Ikale kingdoms, as it was the first settlement of the migrants from the old Benin Kingdom, after the reign of Oba Essigie. The forbear Okoro, who was a general and chief in the Old Benin Kingdom, was the first to settle within the vast geographical territory known as the Ikale Area, which is a part of the division known as Okitipupa Division in the Colonial and Early Post-Colonial Era. The magnitude of the food celebration which Ere ritual festival is known for is captured in an indigenous song in the ̀kálè Dialect. The song goes thus: One ne jije ji ka re 'le Arogbo, one ne mimo ji ka re 'le Arogbo, Larogbo o ne ere, Larogbo o ne sise. Yoruba Translation ̀eni ò ní óúnjẹ kó lọ ilé Alarogbo, ̀eni ò ní omi kó lọ ilé Alarogbo, Alarogbo ní eré, Alarogbo ní s̄s̄ẹ. English Translation He who has nothing to eat should head to Alarogbo's house, he who has nothing to drink should head to Alarogbo's house, Alarogbo has entertainment, Alarogbo has a ceremony. The observance of the Ere festival as celebrated among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa is an extension of what began at Akotogbo, although the Idepe-Okitipupa clan is a separate kingdom in its own right. It is usually observed around late March to early April. After the invasion of Benin, Portuguese allied forces, which decimated the Arogbo-Ule settlement, moved some of the Ikale people in that axis of their homeland to modern day Akotogbo and others to Idepe-Okitipupa, the area/region where this ritual festival holds annually.

Date Range: 1522 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Ikale of Ondo State Nigeria

Region tags: Ikale, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Ondo state

This map shows the Ondo South Senatorial district of Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria where the Ikale people

live and call home.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

↳ Enclosed?

– No

Notes: The ritual takes place in an open setting, as it is predominantly a form of celebration

↳ Elevated?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not take place in an elevated space

↳ By a body of water?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not take place by a body of water, the usual venue of the ritual festival is the front of the palace

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not take place near fire, volcano or lava

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: The Ikale considers every space sacred. In their worldview, there is no distinction between the sacred and the profane.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Specify: usually in front of the palace of the King.

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not take place in an inside setting, since the entire community and guests participate in the ritual, an open space is best suited for the ritual festival.

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual often takes place either at the Enu Owa (Palace front yard) or any other designated spacious place.

Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– No

Notes: The public space is not restricted in any sense, but it is protected by community security so the safety of participants and all attendees is guaranteed.

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not carried out in a private place, rather it takes place in open setting for all members of the community to participate

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– No

Notes: Yes, it is the palace which is the centre of authority in the community

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Field Doesn't Know

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

↳ Was it temporary?

– Yes

Notes: It is temporary. In the case as found in the pictures above, it was carried out on one of the broad streets very close to the palace so more people could participate.

↳ Was it permanent?

– No

Notes: while the space is permanent, the setting for the ritual is only temporal which would be dismantled after the ritual

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Notes: The site associated with the ritual is not found, rather it was created and can be recreated or relocated to another site as the organizers of the ritual deem fit.

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– No

Notes: The site is not associated with any metaphysical concept in particular, however, every site in Ikale thought is connected to the spiritual world

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– No

Notes: The site is not a representative of any physical or metaphysical space

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Notes: The site is not oriented to the sun, stars or other astronomical features.

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Notes: The site does not have a particular directional orientation as participants are sitting facing every direction

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The site is not oriented to landforms like mountains, rivers or coast. It is simply situated in front of the palace called enu owa

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is performed annually

↳ Daily:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed daily but annually

↳ Weekly:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed weekly but annually

↳ Seasonally:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not a seasonal one. It is held annually, usually observed between March and April each year

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed once in an individual lifetime as it is not targeted towards any individual. It is a communal event.

↳ Special events/occasions:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is undoubtedly a special event as the community looks up to its performance every year

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

Notes: The ritual is not connected to marriage, birth or death, as it is not a rite of passage of an individual but the life of the community

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– Yes

Notes: It is usually counted as three weeks after another Festival (okute) among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– No

Notes: The ritual is not measured in hours, it could go on for as long as possible

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– No

Notes: There are no agent, it's entirely community affairs

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve a specialist-patient oriented practices, rather, it a communal celebration hosted by the King

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

Notes: The entire community participate in the ritual, except individuals who profess other faiths. Such individuals refrain from involvement in the ritual as they believe participation is a taboo to their own faith.

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The participants are not numbered, it is believed that the whole community is present

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is not gender sensitive, as male and female are considered important part of the community

↳ Male:

– Yes

Notes: Males are visibly present in their numerous numbers

↳ Female:

– Yes

Notes: Females are also visibly present in their numerous numbers

↳ Transgender:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Non-binary:

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The ritual is not age sensitive. Kids, teens, adults and the elderly are visibly present

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Participants may participate in singing, dancing, drumming as well as cooking for the community

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Participants are not required to be insiders. Outsiders participate, at least, as observers in the ritual festival.

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Insiders and outsiders participate in the ritual celebration

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Participants comprise of both specialists and non-specialists alike

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Of the lot of participants, they fall into the groups of specialists and non-specialists

- ↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?
 - Field Doesn't Know

- ↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?
 - No

Notes: There are no supernatural beings conceived to be participants in the ritual

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

- ↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?
 - No

Notes: Spectators at the ritual are not usually counted. They usually include media houses, journalists, organisations, sponsors and many more.

- ↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:
 - No

Notes: It is not gender specific

- ↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?
 - Specify: The ritual is not age specific

- ↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?
 - No

Notes: Spectators do not have specific roles. They cheer, sing, dance and make the ritual lively although there is a responsibility of maintaining the sacred atmosphere the ritual demands.

- ↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?
 - No

Notes: Spectators are not required to be insiders for this ritual

↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Spectators in the ritual could either be insiders or outsiders

↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: The spectators in the ritual are not required to be ritual specialists

↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Most spectators are non-specialists. However, there is no requirement for them to be one or the other. They could be specialists or otherwise.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no prohibitions for spectators willing to take part in the ritual.

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not have supernatural beings acting in capacity of spectators

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– No

Notes: It is communal, determined by the community through the indigenous leadership structure

Is participation obligatory?

– No

Notes: Individuals have the liberty to decide to or not to participate in the ritual

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– No

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– No

Notes: The ritual is performed annually

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not triggered by hemerological considerations of favourable or unfavourable days

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not observed in response to seasonal change, rather to acknowledge and declare the abundance of harvest from planting of crops in the community.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced in response to natural events

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed in response to any social event

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed in response to an ominous event

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed during any particular life stage

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Notes: This ritual is a stand alone ritual, not part of other rituals

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– Yes

↳ By a government or ruling elite:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not sponsored by the government or ruling elite. Rather, it is mostly sponsored by the King and donors

↳ By NGOs:

Definition: NGO: Non-profit organization

– No

Notes: The ritual is not sponsored by NGOs

↳ By clans or families:

– Yes [specify]: The ruling families and the King's household sponsor the ritual festival

↳ By particular individuals:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals and businesses (as seen in the attached media files) are also allowed to sponsor the ritual festival

↳ Other:

– Specify: Individuals and corporate entities are allowed to display their wares or market their products during the festival as a means of promoting culture and their business interests.

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– No

Notes: The purpose of the ritual is not for maintenance. Rather it is a communal celebration of their abundant harvests.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– No

Notes: The purpose of the ritual is not to cause a change

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– No

Notes: The purpose of the ritual is not devotion. It is to celebrate bounteous harvest in the community

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is held to celebrate the surplus or wealth of the community.

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not for the purpose of propitiation

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

Notes: Domestication of agents is not the purpose of the ritual

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practised to gain information

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for cosmic maintenance

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed to ensure ecological maintenance or stewardship

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced for self transformation

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is performed as gratitude to the divine or supernatural beings for abundance of harvest and abundance of business profits

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed for purification

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed for exorcism purposes

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed for health and healing purposes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed for the purpose of transmitting information, although it serves the purpose of retelling the history of the people and how the ritual celebration connects every member of the community together in shared prosperity.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not performed to obtain luck or fortune

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not a naming ritual

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to improve the community's mode of subsistence.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to induce harm

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not practiced to invoke protection

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with warfare or ritual contests

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with craft practices

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with infanticide

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with gambling or games of chance

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with traveling

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not directly associated with social relations, however, it enhances social relations

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not observed to obtain success but to celebrate it

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– No

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– Yes

↳ Is it individual?

– Yes

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

Notes: there are songs which are rendered in the local dialect.

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

Notes: chanting is also done in the local dialect

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

Notes: prayers are often made for the entire community for peace and tranquility and bountiful harvest for upcoming years

↳ It involves mantras:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve mantras

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve wailing and cheering

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve narrative or recitation

↳ It involves whistling:

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve whistling

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– No

Notes: It does not involve shouting or loud vocalizations

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– No

Notes: The sounds are not produced with parts of the body

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: wooden instruments jammed together to produce sound and a local tambourine

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– No

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

Notes: The sounds are not aerophone

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– Yes

Notes: wooden instruments jammed together to produce sound and a local tambourine

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: up to 10

↳ Is it scripted?

– No

Notes: songs are not scripted

↳ Is it semantic?

– No

Notes: sounds are not semantic

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

Notes: Sounds are not mimetic in anyway

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: Sounds are not restricted to ritual use

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: Sound does not require formal training but indigenous training is required

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– No

Notes: It correlate to the sound of the music being sung

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– No

Notes: The sound is not regulated by pitch

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– No

Notes: The sound does not include pulse

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– No

Notes: The sounds are not codified rather, they are lose

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: determined by the song being sung

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Improvised

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Notes: Objects such as wood being jammed together to produce sound in a certain rhythm

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– Specify: up to 10

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– Yes

Notes: Actors move toward every direction in the process of dancing, they may even touch one another and also throw some stunts

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– Yes

Notes: Actors move toward every direction in the process of dancing, they may even touch one another and also throw some stunts

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– Yes

Notes: Actors move toward every direction in the process of dancing, they may even touch one another and also throw some stunts

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– No

Notes: Movement does not involve ritualised actions

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– Yes

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– No

Notes: Movement are not mimetic in any way

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– No

Notes: Movements do not involve symbolic representation

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– Yes

↳ Is the procession one way?

– No

Notes: The procession is not one way but round trip, from the palace through the centre of the town and then back to the palace

↳ Is the procession multidirectional?

– No

Notes: The procession is not one way but round trip, from the palace through the centre of the town and then back to the palace

↳ Is the procession a roundtrip?

– Yes

Notes: The procession is a round trip, from the palace through the centre of the town and then back to the palace

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve pilgrimage

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– No

Notes: There are no particular or specific posture involved in the ritual

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not involve a particular proximity between participant during the ritual

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no specific body markings done for the purpose of the ritual

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed hair regulations for the purpose of the ritual

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

Notes: tooth modification is not required for the purpose of the ritual

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: Individuals are not required to be partly or fully naked during the ritual

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: scars are not made as part of the ritual

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed piercing for the purpose of the rituals

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

Notes: Genital modification does not take place during the ritual

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no specific shoes to be worn during the ritual

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it removed at some point during the ritual?

– No

Notes: It is for masquerades and it is worn throughout the ritual

↳ Is it added during the ritual?

– No

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not prescribed any clothe color for its participant

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: for the royal households masquerades

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed jewelry or charms used during the ritual

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: by the royal households masquerades

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: There are no materials or objects used during the ritual

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

Notes: Humans are eaten during the ritual

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

↳ Is it a plant:

– Yes

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– No

Notes: The foods eaten during the ritual are not restricted to the ritual celebration alone.

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– No

Notes: The preparation of the food is not ritualised, this is so to encourage members of the community who have devoted themselves to other faith(s) to eat of the food prepared to mark the ritual celebration.

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– No

Notes: The presentation of the food is also not ritualised

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– No

Notes: The food is served in a good portion for participants to eat.

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– No

Notes: The food is not sacralized

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– Yes

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– No

Notes: The food consumed is not associated with healing

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– Yes

Notes: The food consumption happens both onsite and offsite, depending on the choice of the participant

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?

– No

Notes: There is no acknowledgement of any supernatural source of the food

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?

– No

Notes: No environmental source is acknowledged for the provision of the food

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?

– Yes

Notes: Such as sponsors

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– No

Notes: There are no specific types of consumption that are prohibited

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– No

Notes: The substance is not shared from any communal vessel or implement

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Notes: The ritual does not stimulate any form of altered state of consciousness

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– No

Notes: Offerings are not prescribed as part of the ritual, even though an individual may choose to give offering. Such will not be prohibited

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual though determined by number of weeks from Okute in communities like Idepe-Okitipupa and Akotogbo where the latter is being observed. Otherwise, it is a stand-alone ritual generally among the Ikalẹ people.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Notes: The ritual is not part of a sequence of rituals. It is a stand-alone ritual in most parts of Ikaleland.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– No

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– Field Doesn't Know

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– Low

Notes: The ritual gives room for modulation and incorporation of modern practices as much as it does not affect the core of the ritual

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– High

Notes: The ritual involves lots of activities such as dancing, singing, cultural display cooking, eating and drinking

Is there behavioral conformity?

– No

Notes: There are no behavioral conformity prescribed by the ritual

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Field Doesn't Know

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is coordinated by the King and the High Chiefs, then deputised by the chiefs of the Kingdom

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

Notes: The ritual is well planned and well coordinated by the King, his High Chiefs and chiefs who have instituted a planning committee for the ritual celebration

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Preparation usually takes months ahead to ensure a successful execution of the ritual

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– N/A

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

Notes: it involves preparations such as learning of songs, dance steps, chants, and drumming

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed fasting

↳ Does it involve purification:

– No

Notes: There are no prescribed purification in the ritual

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

Notes: leaning such as songs, dance steps, chants, and drumming

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

Notes: There are no form of penance involved in the ritual

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Notes: No form of abstention is prescribed

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The choir members, masquerades and other performers do practise their performance so they could be at their best during the ritual celebration.

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

Notes: To perform the indigenous songs, dances, drumming and more to be presented during the rituals requires high level of expertise. This is a major reason why those involved in these activities need to rehearse or practice well to be at their best during the ritual festival.

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– Specify: four to ten million naira

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– N/A

↳ Other measure of cost:

– N/A

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Exoteric

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

– Through social imitation

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

– Religious specialists

– Political leader(s)

– Social

– Other:: The King, Ijama (High Chiefs), Chiefs and Priest oversee the ritual

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Ere Festival Among the Ikale of Idepe-Okitipupa, Ondo State, Nigeria, Ogen, Olukoya. "Exploring the Potential of Praise Poems for Historical Reconstruction Among the Idepe-ikale in Southeastern Yorubaland" 39 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1353/hia.2012.0002>.

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